

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NCHAPI-MOLOISANE****FIRST NAME: LUCY****PROGRAM CODE : DIRGD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID).

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 16% related to bibliography.

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DIRGD ACA-401D RP6

1. Which of the following statements is a basic step in academic writing?

- Drafting an initial plan including initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic.¹**
- Requesting friends to define the research questions, then select the best.
- Asking the supervisor to devise questions and analyze the tasks.
- Reviewing research articles from journals only for up-to-date information.

2. Which of the following statements best describes plagiarism?

- The writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 34.

- A minor academic offence which carries no consequences.
 - Published work made available and accessible need not be acknowledged.
 - Give credit to the offer when using quotes only.
3. Select the true statement about the storyboard plan researchers build to guide their work.
- The storyboard briefly shows the design of the whole research project.³**
 - It isn't easy to reflect data and ideas on the storyboard.
 - Authors cannot develop arguments on storyboards.
 - Clarity is optional; the writer can explain the visuals.
4. The facts of publication in Turabian Style include three elements. Select one correct answer.
- The place of publication, the publisher's name, and the date (year) of publication.⁴**
 - The name of the organization, editor's first name, and country of publication.
 - The editor's surname, month of publication, and country of publication.
 - The editor's middle name, country of publication, the day of publication.
5. Theses and dissertations can be cited like books, EXCEPT for.
- The title is in Roman type and enclosed in quotation marks.⁵**

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A manual of writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations: Chicago Style for students and researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 32.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 181.

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 202.

- The publisher's name is enclosed in quotation marks.
 - The author's name is written in italics.
 - The year of publication is always in brackets.
6. Select a true statement about the reference list, including two or more works written, edited, or translated by the same individual.
- For all entries after the first, replace the individual's name with a long dash, called a 3-em dash.⁶**
 - For edited or translated works, omit the comma after the dash.
 - Arrange entries in whichever way is convenient.
 - Omit authors with the same name.
7. Which of the following factors contribute to successful dissertation research, according to Sampson (2017). Select the correct statement.
- Visualizing success and good planning.⁷**
 - Communication between the student and the supervisor must focus on the title only.
 - Selecting a dissertation topic that is complex.
 - Formatting the dissertation according to own preference not university guidelines.
8. Choose a statement that describes Sampson's (2017) view about potential bias in qualitative and quantitative research.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 235.

⁷ James Sampson. *A guide to quantitative and qualitative dissertation research*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 13.

- Quantitative researchers contend that answering research questions without bias invalidating the results is possible.⁸**
 - Qualitative researchers contend that answering research questions without bias invalidating the results is possible.
 - Quantitative researchers contend that bias is inherent, yet clarifying it enables the reader to judge if bias influenced the research.
 - It needs to be clarified if quantitative and qualitative researchers acknowledge the existence of potential bias in research.
9. The reference to the European Union's official journal publication is in three (L, C, M) series, each serving a different purpose. Select the correct purpose for the L series.
- L series is about public procurement notices.⁹**
 - L series is about notices and information.
 - L series is about individual interview notices.
 - L series is about notices of recruitment and competitions.
10. WHO is committed to working towards equality between all people and acknowledges the diversity within racial and ethnic groups. Select the appropriate guideline.
- Refer to a person or group's racial or cultural background only when the subject demands it.¹⁰**
 - Older people are frail and mainly suffer from chronic illnesses.
 - Young people are inexperienced and rebellious.

⁸ Sampson, *Quantitative and qualitative dissertation*, 8.

⁹ European Commission. *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Commission: EU Publications, 2021), 93.

¹⁰ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*, Second Edition (World Health Organization, 2013), 56.

- Always make the disability the focus of description when addressing someone with a disability to show empathy.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

European Commission. *English Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. EU Publications, 2021.

Sampson, James, P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Florida: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate, L. *A Manual of Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.